

HOW FOOTBALL TERMS INFLUENCE CULTURE: EXAMPLES FROM UZBEK CULTURE

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Abstract

This thesis explores the profound impact of football terminology on Uzbek culture. Football, as a global phenomenon, not only influences sports but also leaves a lasting mark on language, cultural norms, and identity. Using examples from the Uzbek language and cultural practices, the thesis highlights how borrowed and adapted football terms enrich the Uzbek lexicon and shape societal interactions. The analysis includes historical, linguistic, and sociocultural perspectives, offering insights into the dynamic interplay between sports terminology and cultural identity.

Introduction

Football is more than just a sport; it is a cultural phenomenon that bridges linguistic and societal boundaries. In Uzbekistan, football has gained immense popularity, bringing with it a wave of linguistic borrowings and cultural adaptations. This thesis investigates how football terms, particularly those borrowed from English, influence Uzbek culture. It examines the ways these terms are integrated into the Uzbek lexicon, their semantic shifts, and their role in shaping cultural expressions.

Literature Review

Previous studies on football terminology have primarily focused on linguistic borrowing and translation processes. Researchers like Toshkulov (2023) and Abdullayev (2023) have explored how sports terminology is adapted in different languages. However, there is limited research on the cultural impact of football terms in Uzbekistan. This thesis fills this gap by focusing on the sociocultural dimensions of football terminology and its influence on Uzbek culture.

Methodology

The study employs a qualitative approach, using a combination of linguistic analysis and cultural observation. Data was collected from Uzbek media, football commentary, and interviews with fans and players. The analysis

focuses on the integration of football terms into everyday language, their semantic transformations, and their cultural implications.

Analysis

The analysis reveals that football terms influence Uzbek culture in several ways:

1. **Linguistic Enrichment**: Borrowed terms like 'penalti,' 'korner,' and 'ofsayd' have been seamlessly integrated into Uzbek, often with phonetic and semantic adaptations.
2. **Cultural Identity**: Football terminology is used metaphorically in Uzbek culture to describe teamwork, strategy, and competition.
3. **Media Influence**: Football commentary and journalism popularize these terms, making them part of everyday language.
4. **Social Interaction**: Phrases like 'gol urdi' (scored a goal) are used metaphorically in non-sport contexts to denote success.

Case Studies

The thesis includes case studies highlighting the use of football terms in Uzbek proverbs, advertisements, and social media. For instance, the term 'darvozabon' (goalkeeper) is metaphorically used to describe someone who is a protector or a key decision-maker in a family.

Conclusion

Football terms have a significant impact on Uzbek culture, reflecting the dynamic interplay between global sports and local traditions. They enrich the Uzbek language, shape cultural narratives, and foster a sense of global connection. This thesis underscores the importance of understanding sports terminology as a cultural bridge and invites further research into its broader societal implications.

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